

ISic1252

I.Sicily inscription 1252

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

accounts

Material

breccia

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492858

EDCS 39101620

PHI 140740

PHI 175715

PHI 329617

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin.

At 14.0427 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 45.1342

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Arangio Ruiz, V., Olivieri, A. 1925. Inscriptiones graecae Siciliae et infimae Italiae ad ius pertinentes. Milan. At no.7

Bechtel, F., Collitz, H., Meister, R. C., Bezzenberger, A. 1884-1915. Sammlung der griechischen Dialekt-Inschriften. Göttingen. At 5225

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